

The Long Duration of the Ongoing Wave of Accumulation: An Update of Ernest Mandel's Model in the Era of State Neoliberalism

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Abstract

Ernest Mandel developed an original and comprehensive analysis of capitalism. Among his most important contributions is his controversial theory of long waves of accumulation. This article builds on this framework and attempts to update it for the current period. The theory of long waves must be articulated together with processes of accumulation by dispossession, the theory of absolute advantages, the theory of uneven development and the role of empowered labour in global productivity. All of these are determined by socio-political and endogenous development dynamics. We will attempt to

characterise the transformations and current status of the ongoing long wave, and the possible reasons for its protracted duration. The article also attempts to characterise the actually-existing model of neoliberalism in which the state plays a leading role.

Keywords

Long Waves – Ernest Mandel – Uneven Development – Financialisation – Global Capitalism – State Neoliberalism

Introduction

The analysis of the long-run economy has been addressed by different schools of thought such as the Annales School¹; the geographic-social vision;² the great hegemonic changes in the world-economy;³ or the long systemic cycles of accumulation driven by hegemonic powers in the mercantile and financial spheres.⁴ Other analytical frameworks, such as that of the regulation school,⁵ attribute a central importance to the state and the medium-term to characterise

¹ Braudel 1995.

² Harvey 2003.

³ Wallerstein 1974.

⁴ Arrighi 2010.

⁵ Aglietta 1979.

different modes of development, accumulation regimes and social structures of accumulation⁶.

Ernest Mandel was arguably the most comprehensive Marxist economist of the second half of the Twentieth century. However, decades later, in a context of ideological regression and the retreat of Marxism to academia and the avant-garde, his interpretative framework requires an update.

The transition of countries from real socialism to capitalism, the rise of China and other emerging countries, the policies of state financialised neo-liberalism, technological innovations and the renewal in the oligopolistic accumulation regime have brought qualitative changes in the dynamics of accumulation. These dynamics have expanded the available labour force and fluidified the mobility of capital, interconnecting global value chains. They have done so over two singular periods. The first from the 1990s until 2007, with the implementation of a new generation of neoliberal measures that only partially coincided with the doctrine of the neoclassical school. More than a few authors called for abandoning the concept of the long wave, or else to consider registering the inauguration of a new one. Since 2008, with new contradictions added, there has been a clear

⁶ McDonough 2021, p.15.

tendency towards stagnation. A trend of increasingly weak and uneven growth, which reflects the slowed pace of accumulation in large parts of the world.

Ernest Mandel's polymathic and scientific vocation make his work an obligatory reference for understanding capitalist development during the Twentieth century. Mandel built and strengthened an open Marxism linked to the movement of the real. However, it needs to be updated as Mandel himself, having passed away in 1995, cannot do this.

In this contribution, we first recall Mandel's interpretation of long waves. Then, we critically review some of the main debates surrounding his contributions. Finally, we develop some considerations for interpreting the latest phase of world capitalist development. This paper attempts to bring order to these debates.

The Long Waves Accumulation Model

Long wave theory has been approached from different angles. Kondratieff launched a long-view empirical and statistical research programme which has had multiple heirs. Since then, different

schools have taken his applied studies to adopt their own analytical reading.

Schumpeter inaugurated a school within the dominant economics paradigm which gave dynamism and depth to its theoretical framework. Sometimes referred to as the Innovation School⁷, it has taken on a life of its own, at times plural, open and critical, far from the mainstream perspective of its founder though still emphasising the role of technological change.⁸

Some schools adopting the long wave notion base their studies on collecting indicators on prices, output, innovation and inventions, capital investment, trade, real wages and working-class behaviour.⁹ Other approaches are more multidimensional¹⁰ and analyse the culture, politics, economics, geography, science and social circumstances which shape institutions, technology and production dynamics.

Trotsky built on Kondratieff's empirical data to study the curves of capitalist development¹¹ through an open Marxism. It is against this research background and with these same references and material,

⁷ Led by scholars such as Gerhard Mensch, Christopher Freeman and Carlota Pérez, among others, cited by Gutiérrez, 2001, p.1292.

⁸ Carlota Pérez 2002 and 2015, prefers, for instance, the term 'great surges' to 'long wave'.

⁹ Goldstein 1988 quoted by Gutiérrez, 2019, p.1287. Other approaches linked to the use of statistics are those close to the capital investment School, led by Jay Forrester, Gutiérrez, 2019, p. 1292.

¹⁰ Freeman and Louçã 2001, pp.125–6.

¹¹ Trotsky 1923.

that Ernest Mandel updated and strengthened Marxist theory. Mandel created a new paradigm¹² with distinct features within contemporary Marxism for a long-term analytical perspective.

Capitalism began from a process of original accumulation, linked to plunder, appropriation and colonisation.¹³ This made it easier for industrialisation to develop first in the imperialist countries. While capitalism imposed itself by plundering and appropriating the wealth of the planet, it consolidated by exploiting the value produced by labour. With the establishment of new social relations, the bourgeois state and the logic of the commodity spread, and the logic of capital accumulation became the predominant economic dynamic. The bourgeois social relations of production, once established, determined and channelled the development of the productive forces. Mandel's contribution was originally inspired by the early works of Leon Trotsky, which were the result of the debate around Kondratieff's studies¹⁴ and analysed 'the laws of motion and the history of capital'¹⁵. In this framework, the dynamic of accumulation is driven, mainly but not exclusively, by the long-term rate of profit.¹⁶ Accumulation

¹² Other authors have also been classified in this school of capitalist crisis, following Gutiérrez 2019, such as Tylecote 1992, Gordon 1980, Screpanti 1984, among others.

¹³ Mandel 1999, p.345.

¹⁴ Kondratieff 1998; Day, 1981.

¹⁵ Mandel 1999, p.13.

¹⁶ Mandel 1999, pp. 114–15; Mandel 1995.

describes long expansive and depressive periods¹⁷, conditioned by social and political disputes and possible countertrends¹⁸.

For Mandel, long waves do not operate mechanically or by chance. Long waves are long-term movements in the dynamic of accumulation that are set in motion only once the relations of production that guide investment and business have been established. This behaviour depends on multiple epochal factors,¹⁹ determined by international hegemony, inter-imperialist tensions, the state of technology, the availability of raw materials, the access to and shaping of markets, the dynamics and financial structure of the investment chain, the type of socio-historical formations and states. It also depends on factors of the dynamic of accumulation itself and the formation and the evolution of the rate of profit, which in turn depends on the forms of labour exploitation and socio-technical aspects of production.

Within these waves, shorter cycles are also observed: periodic industrial cycles – resulting from the oscillation of aggregate supply and demand and inventory accumulation²⁰ – and, in the medium term,

¹⁷ Mandel 1995, idea taken up by Albarracín 1987.

¹⁸ Albarracín 2010.

¹⁹ Mandel 1999, p.39.

²⁰ Shaikh 2010.

fluctuations resulting from the mismatch between the production cycle of heavy industry and fixed capital and that of light industry.

Struggles at different levels – political, ideological, organisational, social, labour and others – determine the start of each long wave and the form its development will take. Their dynamics also respond to a tension between technical and economic factors. Other related theoretical schools²¹ have similarly described these necessary social and political changes and referred to them as social structures of accumulation. While they offer an interesting socio-institutional and historical reading, their interpretation places an important weight on social accords and reforms and a consensual mode of social regulation to sustain productivity gains. Mandel, on the other hand, considered that the answers were forged out of a conflict that left no room for concessions, believing that there could not be a harmonious solution within capitalism.

Although the first three completed long waves had the same duration, this is not necessarily prescribed by the model. They started with a period of prosperity of about 25 years and then endogenously entered a period of decline lasting a similar length of time. However, the transition from a phase of depression to one of prosperity required

²¹ Gutiérrez 2019, pp.1295; McDonough, McMahon and Kotz 2021.

qualitative social and political changes to restore the rate of profit to its norm at a level sufficient to vigorously sustain accumulation.

Let us summarise the first three long waves. The first long wave took place in the first half of the Nineteenth century, when England replaced France as the hegemonic power in 1763 when the Treaty of Paris was signed, confirming the British victory in the Seven Years' War against France and forcing the latter to cede much of its colonial empire. New bourgeois institutions and capitalist relations displaced the vestiges of the old feudal regime and any other previous forms of production. The dominant technology was based on manufactures and coal. The first Industrial Revolution took place with the defeat of the old nobility and peasantry. The new impoverished proletariat, despite explosive, dispersed and heavily repressed cycles of international mobilisation – such as the Peoples' Spring of 1848 – did not change this. In addition, capitalist expansion built or forced its way into new markets that offered conditions for profitable development.

The second long wave, in the second half of the Nineteenth century, found with the age of imperialism, the steam engine, iron and steel and electricity, all the conditions for the expansion of the Second Industrial Revolution. Antagonistic socio-political organisations, such as the First International, were still only just beginning to contribute to the formation of the labour movement, and their influence was still

limited, despite the experience of the 1871 Paris Commune. A large part of the workers' movement finally embraced national banners and social-democratic demands. The radical organisations were harshly repressed. In its depressive phase, the availability of raw materials and new techniques and the opening of new markets provided favourable conditions for the expansion of the next long wave.

As for the third wave, in the first half of the Twentieth century, oil, plastics, Taylorism and the formation of large companies enabled its boom phase under the rule of the imperialist bourgeoisie. Capitalism saw its structures shaken by two major world and inter-imperialist wars, with a crisis of overproduction between the two conflagrations. But in that period, new paths also opened up, alternative regimes were formed, and the labour movement conquered state power, waged civil wars and carried out revolutions. Under intense harassment, these new workers states degenerated and became bureaucratized, and after several decades of survival became exhausted. As a result of these struggles of the labour movement, in the new regimes and in the capitalist states themselves, important social policies and rights were introduced as well as complementary indirect wages among the working class in the West.

Mandel's most original work focused on the fourth long wave, or as he described it, Late Capitalism.²² This wave only began its ascendant phase after enormous social and political sacrifices. It took a long period of fascism, disciplinary and protectionist policies, and a genocidal World War II for the rate of profit to rise and usher in a new period of accumulation.

Mandel²³ coined the term 'parametric determinism', inspired by Karl Marx's view that 'Men make their own history, but not under conditions of their own choosing'.²⁴ The concept of parametric determinism²⁵ considers that it is possible to express algebraically a series of structural determinations without falling into automatism. It links multiple socio-economic factors with their own dynamics to show possible trends and tensions. For instance, the rate of exploitation, driven by class struggle, is mediated by forms of labour organisation, labour regulations, and direct or indirect wage conditions; the organic composition of capital depends on the forms and dynamics of investment, the designs and uses of sciences and technology, and the relationship between technical resources and labour, among other factors. These endogenous factors in the dynamics of capital

²² Mandel 1999.

²³ Mandel 2018, see part IV.

²⁴ Marx 1963

²⁵ Mandel within the foreword's Albarracín, 1987, p.14.

relations, along with other structural and contextual factors in each era shape the trends in the rate of profit.

While the rate of profit is an influential factor guiding the logic of accumulation, it is not the only one. This rate is mainly related to the rate of exploitation and the organic composition of capital, being the rate of return = $s/(c+v)$ = rate of surplus value/(occ+1); where the rate of surplus value is s/v and occ is the organic composition of capital (c/v). Moreover, in a more sophisticated analysis²⁶, it is not enough to look at the gross aggregate components of the rate of profit themselves. The relationship between the rate of profit and the rate of accumulation must be refined. A fall in the rate of profit would not be enough for the rate of accumulation to start falling. There must also be a fall in the overall mass of profits²⁷. In turn, the rate of profit that best guides investment is the one considered by firms and not the overall rate of profit (which would add up the gross profits of firms – the return on working capital – plus the interest they earn on financial capital). The profit rate of firms – the net profit rate, or effective profit rate – is the difference between the rate of profit before tax and the interest rate capitalists must pay back to finance their capital, always measured in real terms, without inflation.

²⁶ Shaikh 2010.

²⁷ Shaikh 1992.

For Mandel, these factors are 'endogenous' to the dynamic of accumulation. These factors which define the profit rate are, in turn, determined by multiple socio-economic dynamics.

The rate of exploitation is influenced by several factors: First, by the correlation of forces embodied in labour regulations, collective agreements, contractual forms, wage conditions, labour rights and associated social rights. Second by the forms of work organisation, the length of the working day, the intensity of work and the contribution of productivity to the surplus. In all of these, class conflict is fundamental.

Economic, social, productive and technical dimensions help determine the organic composition of capital. In particular, the degree of inter-firm competition, the degree of mechanisation, overall productivity developments, the availability and productive power of materials and real wages. It should be made clear that the productivity indicator should be interpreted with caution, and will be used here as a proxy, since the overall productivity of the factors of production does not necessarily align with labour productivity and is affected by possible statistical composition effects. Consider, for instance, the paradox that occurs when the indicator increases, while employment decreases and production remains the same, or when labor

productivity increases and total factor productivity may not if there is no more efficient use of capital and labour together.

A word of caution is needed before one can understand the rate of profit in relation to the organic composition of capital. Mandel, in general, pointed out that there is an upward trend in the latter, but did not pay much attention to its analysis, as if assuming that it was the result of technical change and competition. By contrast, Jacques Gouverneur²⁸ and Michel Husson²⁹ in their more precise analyses argued that its evolution depends on:

- a) The degree of mechanisation, which tends to increase.
- b) The evolution of the ratio of unit values (Value of the means of production/Value of the means of consumption, which depends on the trend of productivity).
- c) Real wages which depend on the balance of power between labour and capital and the cost of reproduction of labour power.

Thus, the organic composition of capital depends on multiple factors, some of which are non-mechanical.

²⁸ Gouverneur 2001, p. 63.

²⁹ Husson 2003.

The profit rate is determined by several factors, with the endogenous ones primarily being those linked to dynamics of capital accumulation. But the latter is also influenced by exogenous factors related to social, institutional and contextual historical components like: a country's situation within the international division of labour, social unrest, the effects of war, energy or raw material crises, climate, or the state of technology, among others.

The dividing line between endogenous and exogenous factors is sometimes blurred. However, this pedagogical differentiation has a clear meaning: the internal dynamics of capital do not operate in a vacuum, and it is decisive, in order to describe a trend, to take into account the epochal context of each accumulation regime.

Endogenous - Exogenous Factors in Laws of Motion of Capital³⁰

³⁰ Source: Own elaboration based on Mandel's considerations, 1999, regarding to endogenous and exogenous factors.

Mandel used an ‘endogenous-exogenous’ division, which is useful if these terms are clearly explained and linked to the specific context. The idea of endogeneity is used to facilitate the understanding and analysis of accumulation itself, with the possibility of finding porous borders with what is considered exogenous. This division between exogenous and endogenous factors affirms the tendency to crisis, intrinsic to the logic of capital, but which can also be countered by factors outside this logic. Class struggles is a crucial such factor, alongside others such as the arms race,³¹ wars, the

³¹ Freeman and Louçã 2001, p.254.

discovery of new markets and raw materials, imperialist disputes and colonialism³² or the role of the state.³³ Mandel's way of presenting the problem was a way of challenging Schumpeter's self-restoring, who based his work on the idea of creative destruction and innovation to conceive of a capitalism that is renewed throughout business cycles, in a way similar to that argued by Alan Freeman.³⁴

This approach distinguishes itself from both those who deny the role of the rate of profit and those who consider it the sole explanatory factor.³⁵ This view therefore gives rise to a structural interpretation open to other historical factors: the hegemonic role of the imperialist powers, the relationship between centres and peripheries, the question of dependency relations and territory as well as the importance of ecology.

Mandel focused on several factors in long waves which, due to their direct relation to the logic of capital, were bound to cause recurrent crises and stagnation phases with more frequent recessions. However, he did not rule out and instead actually studied how at three different times in history long recessionary waves had turned into expansionary ones. Mandel's main conclusion is that this

³² Mandel, 1999 p. 343.

³³ Mandel, 1999 p. 474.

³⁴ Freeman 2014.

³⁵ Roberts 2016.

change was not due to endogenous factors – meaning the logic of accumulation itself – but to factors exogenous to the profit-driven logic of capital. During the Nineteenth century’s industrial revolution, the combination of growing availability of energy and raw materials with new markets to be conquered and a huge world labour force facilitated the transition from the first to the second long wave. In the Twentieth century, the transition from the third to the fourth long wave was the result of two main factors:

(a) the industrial destruction of the Second World War, which facilitated the introduction of new technologies and provided new market opportunities for new investment; and

b) the defeat of the working class, which accepted lower wages and a huge intensification of work to cope with the war.

The Austrian school, with Joseph A. Schumpeter³⁶ as the most prominent figure, argued that the main engines of expansive cycles were savings, sacrifice and above all the initiative of the captains of industry³⁷ who promoted technological innovation.³⁸ However, technological factors do not trigger the onset of the long wave. The

³⁶ Schumpeter 2017.

³⁷ Schumpeter 1996.

³⁸ Schumpeter 1934.

shift to a new technological paradigm, which must have accumulated a stock of fundamental knowledge, inventions and potential patents, does not occur until it materialises in new investments stimulated by a previous increase in the rate of profit. This requires conditions in which reconstruction becomes a business opportunity, when the destruction or devaluation of machinery embodying old technologies opens an opportunity for the introduction of the new. Although technological change is not the root cause, its generalisation contributes to the greater strength and duration³⁹ of the expansionary phase, as was the case until the early 1970s.⁴⁰ The reconstruction and application of technologies in new investments, such as microelectronics, robotics, synthetic fibres, or new energy extraction systems, such as nuclear energy, emerged in the decades following the post-war period. In summary, the third scientific and technological revolution developed when market conditions and profitability⁴¹ were favourable and not before.⁴²

From 1990 onwards, the world capitalist economy expanded in Eastern Europe and Asia and productive value chains were

³⁹ Louçã, 2021.

⁴⁰ Albarracín 1987, p. 73. Jesús Albarracín (1943–2001) was a Spanish economist and disciple of Ernest Mandel.

⁴¹ Freeman and Louçã 2001, p.337. These authors concede a higher importance for the technological factor, but they admit that the downswing phase begins with a falling profit rate, linked to rising costs of inputs. They do argue that reasons are needed beyond technology to explain a new long wave.

⁴² Albarracín 2022, p.442.

consolidated on a global scale. Western countries implemented neoliberal policies favouring the creation of fictitious capital – expansive monetary policies and debt creation. A new generation of innovations in the field of the third scientific revolution made its way into the world economy. These developments took place after the death of Mandel and added complexity to the expected course of the fourth long wave. We are therefore going through a transition since the 1990s in which the foundations of capitalist development are changing. The debate about the extent of this change is ongoing.

Towards an Update of Ernest Mandel's Long Wave Model

The Behaviour of the Last Long Wave

Mandel's most successful contribution was his analysis of the fourth long wave.⁴³ He predicted the crisis of the 1970s and anticipated the start of the stagnation phase of the fourth long wave. However, after the 1970s profitability crisis, the rate of profit rose again⁴⁴ from the 1980s until 2005.⁴⁵ Although far from attaining the growth rates of the

⁴³ Mandel 1995.

⁴⁴ Louçã 2019.

⁴⁵ Husson 2013.

post-war ascendant phase, it partially recovered its vigour until 2008. How can we interpret this situation which seems to contradict Mandel's forecasts?

Seventy years after it started, the state of this long wave is still being debated. In the core countries of the West and in Japan, it seems to have lasted longer than previous waves. The weak and erratic growth that followed the crises of 2000, 2008 and 2020 – and in Japan the stagnation that began in 1990 – show the exhaustion of the fourth long wave's vigour. The recovery in the rate of return may have been limited to just over three five-year periods with a clear inflection point after 2008.

Against this background, the principle of uneven and combined development⁴⁶ becomes relevant. The combination of old and new forms of production relations does not play the role it used to. There is an ongoing debate amongst different authors about the length, regularity and diverse regional behaviour of long waves.

Some authors focus on how the present long wave has lasted longer than expected.⁴⁷ They point to the weakness of accumulation, due either to the detraction of financial costs from profitability, or to

⁴⁶ Claudio Katz 2019, in the seminar on 'Contemporary Capitalism' held at the Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Buenos Aires (IEALC), offered this suggestive reflection.

⁴⁷ Louçã 2019 and Husson 2013.

the weakness of global productivity. Michael Roberts⁴⁸ and Harman⁴⁹ adopt a mechanistic perspective, turning the theory of the falling rate of profit into a monocausal explanation. They describe a saw-shaped but persistent falling trend in the rate of profit lasting 70 years, which constrains investment possibilities.

Claudio Katz⁵⁰ finds the concept of a long wave unsatisfactory, given the model's weak ability to account for novelties and unforeseen impulses. He prefers the term stage, although he is not the first one to use this concept.⁵¹ Inspired by David Harvey,⁵² Katz focuses on the model of uneven and combined development of globalised capital as a more solid interpretation, which in his view is the only one capable of incorporating the mutation of global capitalism with the irruption of China and technological change.

Katz's recovery of the theory of unequal development helps us understand the relationship of dependence between centres, semi-peripheries and peripheries, as well as the phenomena of the emergence, rise and fall of new powers. It bears in mind the role of class conflict that occurs in all these territories. We believe that the

⁴⁸ Roberts 2016.

⁴⁹ Harman 200.

⁵⁰ Katz 2018.

⁵¹ Maddison 2001, a British economic historian who collected and organised the statistics of numerous countries over the very long term, using an empiricist and comparative method, which was very useful for following large macroeconomic indicators. Although he identified the existence of stages and, on occasions, cycles, he was alien to the Marxist method.

⁵² Harvey 2003.

territorial articulation of uneven development with long wave theory requires more attention. Only by looking at each socio-historical formation in each significant territory within the global value chain can we understand the relationships and dynamics of development and their mutual implications in global capitalism. However, it does not seem appropriate to abandon the notion of the long wave. This analysis does not require a change in the fundamental patterns of the long wave, but these insights cannot be ignored.

Class struggles influence the factors that favour or impede tendencies of accumulation. They can even provoke shifts and ruptures, transforming the very basis of overall economic dynamics. Once the rules are changed, whether in capitalism or in a post-capitalist society, trends are altered and abstract analyses become meaningless. Long-wave patterns, with their corresponding internal contradictions, must therefore be confined to the institutional, geopolitical and productive framework of a period of time in which they remain relatively stable. The incorporation of history and human agency are key, although they do not operate outside of inherited structures, but from them.

Only when socio-economic foundations are consolidated is it possible to identify trends in waves and cycles. In a favourable context, the global restoration of the rate of profit has two

preconditions: The first is the recovery of the rate of surplus value, which may have been boosted by some of its basic underlying factors⁵³. Real unit labour costs, which refer to relative surplus value and relative wages, stagnant in previous years, have been clearly falling after 2021, a trend that international institutions expect to persist.

Real Unit labour costs (Nominal unit labour costs divided by GDP price deflator) (percentage change on preceding year, 2003–2023)⁵⁴

	5 years averages						Spring 2022 forecast		
	2003-2007	2008-2012	2013-2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Euroarea	-0,7	0,9	-0,4	0,4	0,1	2,3	-2,1	-1,6	-1
EU	-1,1	0,7	-0,5	0,4	-0,1	2,4	-2,7	-1,8	-1,1
UK	0,8	-0,4	-0,2	0,1	1,5	6,7	-3	-1,7	-0,2
Japan	-0,3	-0,1	-0,8	2,6	1,3	2,4	-0,5	-1,2	-2,1
United States	-0,6	-0,5	0,1	-0,4	0,1	2,9	-1	-0,5	-0,1

⁵³ Husson 2013, p.8

⁵⁴ Taken from European Commission. European Economic Forecast. Spring 2022. Institutional, paper 173 / May 2022 Statistical Annexes. p. 165.

The second precondition is a relative decline in the organic composition of capital. This requires a strong destruction of fictitious and productive capital, perhaps through a severe economic crisis. It would require, at the very least, widespread corporate destruction due to insolvencies and a debt or financial crisis,⁵⁵ or another depressive phenomenon such as a war. Capitalist policies have been deferring this massive destruction of capital. The sharp shift in 2022 towards a traditional restrictive monetary policy will probably lead to a recession by raising financial costs. The effective rate of return⁵⁶ on capital, as well as the cost of public debt – which has reached historically high levels – may suffer as a result. What is certain is that the ruling classes will continue to focus on the exploitation⁵⁷ of labour and on international competition for raw materials. This may lead, as the war in Ukraine shows, to an extension of conflict.

Two additional contextual notes for the period are worth making. The stagnant historical trend in productivity – save for the 1995–2004 digital revolution period⁵⁸ and its average annual growth of 5% – does not augur well for any strong recovery.

⁵⁵ Toussaint 2015

⁵⁶ Shaikh 2010

⁵⁷ Mandel 1999, p. 341.

⁵⁸ Chesnais 2019

Labour Productivity Changes⁵⁹

The Asian economy centred around China also shows insufficient productivity growth. The gap with the West has narrowed, but China is still far from reaching US productivity levels, according to ILO data.⁶⁰ China's competitive strength relies on factors like low labour costs, the large availability of labour and its control of significant industrial and technological segments.

⁵⁹ Source: Own elaboration based in European Commission. European Economic Forecast. Spring 2022. Institutional, paper 173 / May 2022 Statistical Annexes. Page 164.

⁶⁰ Vázquez 2021

World Productivity Rate⁶¹

We must also bear in mind that, in terms of the net availability of energy and raw materials, the carrying capacity of the planet has already been exceeded and the situation is worsening.⁶²

Productivity calculations are usually broken down into several factors aside from labour productivity. The World Bank⁶³ has shown that for advanced, emerging and less industrialised economies human capital explains a smaller share of global productivity and that the most important productivity drivers have been capital deepening and, especially, total factor productivity: the result of the more efficient use of human labour, physical capital, and technology. In the period under study, 1980–2018, overall productivity in advanced countries

⁶¹ Source: Own calculation on World Bank statistics.

⁶² Fernández and González 2018

⁶³ Dieppe, 2021 <https://www.worldbank.org/en/research/publication/global-productivity>

tended to stagnate. In the period 2003–2008, emerging economies increased their productivity by 5%, advanced economies by just 1.5%, and the less industrialised economies grew by 3%. In the period 2013–2018, advanced economies grew by 0.8%, emerging economies by 3.4% and less industrialised economies by 2.4%.

As we have already noted, while Michel Husson,⁶⁴ or François Chesnais⁶⁵ and Francisco Louçã⁶⁶ consider that we are in a long decline phase of the fourth long wave, Claudio Katz abandons the concept and adopts that of a stage. The period 1990–2008 has also been interpreted by some scholars⁶⁷ as the beginning of a new long wave, the fifth, also referred to as the neoliberal stage.

It is more appropriate to view it as an oscillation, like a wave within the fourth long wave, which makes it longer than the previous ones. Its causes lie in the implementation of a unique neo-liberal state regime which has combined a rise in exploitation rates, banking deregulation policies, a monetary policy favourable to capital and the transitory improvement in productivity. This situation has allowed the rate of profit to partially recover and facilitated a significant if lesser vigour in accumulation. But it has also brought contradictions that,

⁶⁴ Husson 2013.

⁶⁵ Chesnais 2019.

⁶⁶ Louçã 2019.

⁶⁷ Among others, Pérez 2015, Malm 2018, Braña 2020, or Gutiérrez 2019.

from 2008 onwards, has caused a downward phase characterised by high levels of public debt, the transgression of ecological limits, environmental degradation and more expensive raw materials and energy. It has also led to greater geostrategic tensions affecting international value chains.⁶⁸

Were it not for the fact that until 2022 interest rates had remained very low, recession would have deepened. Zombie companies survived and fictitious capital that would otherwise have disappeared was sustained.

These circumstances have led to a severe investment crisis. The 2014–2019 cycle has been a typical industrial cycle that gave way to a slowdown which fell into depression with the pandemic. This has been followed by an intense but short recovery. By 2022 the economic cycle has confirmed the trend towards either stagnation or recession depending on the country.

According to IMF estimates, in 2023 advanced economies would have grown by just 1.2%. Emerging economies would continue to grow, but only at a rate of 4%, and Germany would have entered recession.

⁶⁸ Albarracín 2023.

The changes observed at the global level do not allow us to ascertain whether we are facing a new upward phase. But we cannot rule it out either, particularly if in the future certain transformations – digitalisation, teleworking, fragmentation of the world of work, disciplinary control, wage depression or others – significantly raise the rate of exploitation and destroy part of the surplus capital. But the extent of this remains to be seen. History does not stand still and the political action of the workers' movement plays a fundamental role in the way in which the systemic contradictions that emerge will be played out.

Uneven Development, Value Transfers and Real Divergence

Mandel took the schema of uneven and combined development to study capitalism on a global scale. He observed that the Third World, as the countries of the South were called during the Cold War, were trapped by imperialism in relations of dependency.

To understand uneven development, he focused first on the violence of original accumulation, and second on the profit formation of corporate oligopolies in imperialist countries. In this way, he attributed to the presence of dual rates of profit the generation of value

transfers⁶⁹ from the periphery to the centre, where the central oligopoly capital was located.

To explain the transfers of value, Mandel explains that in the period of classical imperialism:

International movements of capital constantly reproduce and extend the international productivity differential which is characteristic of the history of modern capitalism, and are themselves in turn further determined by this differential ... In the classical imperialism period the main form of surplus-profits originated from the differences between the rates of profit in the metropolitan countries and the colonies.⁷⁰

These transfers were due to a lower organic composition of capital in the colonies than that existing in the heavy and light industries of the metropolitan countries. It was also due to a higher rate of surplus value in the colonies, driven by greater production of absolute surplus value and the presence of an industrial reserve army that allowed the price of labour-power to fall further.⁷¹ This difference in the average rate of profit slowed down accumulation in the colonies because part

⁶⁹ Mandel 1999, pp.350–1.

⁷⁰ Mandel 1999 p.343.

⁷¹ Mandel 1999, p.344.

of the extracted surplus value was transferred to the metropolitan countries, favouring their own accumulation or the distribution of dividends in the metropolis.

To this dynamic of extraordinary profit transfer was added another 'mechanism of exploitation':⁷² unequal exchange, which after the phase of classical imperialism prevailed over the former. 'This unequal exchange meant that colonies and semi-colonies tended to exchange increasing amounts of indigenous labor (or products of labor) for a constant amount of metropolitan labor'.⁷³ It was not until after the interwar period that the transfer of extraordinary profits was surpassed by unequal exchange,⁷⁴ coinciding with the substitution of the monopoly capitalism of classical imperialism by an oligopolistic regime inserted in value chains and global competition.

From World War II onwards, anti-imperialist movements in newly independent countries were able to hinder the transfer of extraordinary profits from transnational monopolies from the colonies to the metropolises. From that moment on, transfers decreased in comparative terms to other profit factors. Unequal exchange became more important and the transfers would circulate through formulas of economic domination that were not as direct as the transfer prices.

⁷² Mandel 1999, p.345.

⁷³ Mandel 1999, p.345.

⁷⁴ Mandel 1999, p.346.

Behind unequal exchange lies an exchange of unequal quantities of labour, based on two sources:

1. The fact that the labor of the industrialized countries counts as more intensive (hence more productive of value) on the world market than that of the underdeveloped lands...
2. The fact that no equalisation of the rates of profit occurs on the world market, where different national prices of production (average rates of profit) exist side by side and are articulated with one another.⁷⁵

This is equivalent to a combination of the effect of empowered labour, understood as work that improves its productivity by making use of technology superior to that existing in its branch. This was observed by Marx, is insisted upon by Astarita,⁷⁶ and is something which Mandel already takes into consideration. Just as Mandel takes into account a transfer of values from that unevenness of profit rates between regions of the world. Transfers caused by the existence of different organic compositions of capital, which explains the type of

⁷⁵ Mandel 1999, p. 351.

⁷⁶ Astarita 2023, p. 69.

international mobility of capitals and the unequal and combined development.⁷⁷

This dynamic also explains the tendency of 'the long-term development of wages [which] is dependent on the long-term trend of the industrial reserve army and the long-term trend in the productivity of labour in the consumer goods sector and agriculture', allowing wages to fall below the subsistence minimum.⁷⁸ This implies generalising for the countries of the Global South what for Marx was rather a temporary exception: super-exploitation.

With several exceptions, he envisaged an absolute impoverishment, as Marini⁷⁹ argued, of most countries in the South. However, there have been processes of industrialisation, expansion of employment and even of real wage growth, which are compatible with the fall in the share of income going to labour in the national income of each country. Although there has been a widespread phenomenon of real divergence, growing the relative distance between North and South, this has not prevented growth processes in absolute terms in most of the peripheral countries.

Many economies of the Global South have experienced sustained growth in recent decades. The predicted absolute

⁷⁷ Mandel 1999, p. 361.

⁷⁸ Mandel 1999, p. 362.

⁷⁹ Marini 1998.

impoverishment has not become widespread, not to mention the fact that a selective group of emerging countries is even competing for the global market with the classic Western countries. Even the least developed countries, according to the UN classification⁸⁰, have increased their per capita income, in a positive evolution, at least since 1995 and 2019.

GDP Growth for Least Developed Countries⁸¹

Internal inequalities have widened and in relative terms, a large part of the economies of the Global South suffer from a lower degree of development than the countries of the North. This is especially so in terms of human development, access to basic services and

⁸⁰ United Nations 2022 available at: <<https://www.un.org/en/conferences/least-developed-countries#:~:text=Afganist%C3%A1n%2C%20Angola%2C%20Bangladesh%2C%20Benin,%2C%20Malawi%2C%20Mal%C3%AD%2C%20Mauritania%2C>>.

⁸¹ Source: Own elaboration based on World Bank Data.

infrastructures and a greater dependence on global value chains of the old and new powers. That the impoverishment of nations has not become generalised in absolute terms does not mean that the growing world population does not suffer greater economic inequality relative to the ruling classes at the national level and relative to the main centres of development. There has been a joint process of new dependent peripheralisation, relative impoverishment and growing inequality, which is also compatible with the economic irruption of a series of emerging economies.

The unequal remuneration of labour is the result of differentiated productivity levels, wages and working conditions, depending on the position of the economic sectors in which they are employed within the global value chain. This too has an unequal character, based on an international division of labour defined by an imperialist hierarchy.

In short, unequal and combined development would no longer be so much affected by monopolistic dynamics, but by the factors of empowered labour: that is, by the weight of the value created by labor through technological environments that enhance its production in a differential and competitively differentiated way, as well as by a value transfer that results from the dynamics of unequal rates of profitability between economic regions of the world. These value transfer occur in the joint process of production and commercial valorisation, first in

the extraction of surplus value, second in competition and finally in commercialisation, no longer so much within the monopolistic circuit, but through the complex competition of the global value chain.

Mandel also points out how, after World War II, local bourgeoisies managed to retain some of the surplus value previously appropriated by foreign bourgeoisies through monopolies. They did this by limiting foreign capital to 50% in domestic companies and strategic sectors.⁸² This policy is still maintained, for example, in the Cuban, Vietnamese, Belarusian or Chinese cases.

Contrary to possible misinterpretations of Mandel's thought,⁸³ Mandel does assume that exploitation comes first and then there is an appropriation of the surplus by international and national capital. This appropriation takes place now through regional oligopolistic business groups marked by their own medium-term business cycles and global competition.

At the same time, the influence of the oligopolistic regime that Mandel highlights in the course of late capitalism is an observation for the specific historical period of his analysis. He emphasises this point to account for a transformation from the monopolistic capitalism of classical imperialism to one based on an oligopolistic regime. This

⁸² Mandel 1999, p. 348.

⁸³ Albarracín 2023, p.8.

regime of competition operates with tensions along global value chains and across cycles where oligopolies are periodically renewed. Oligopolies, which can become monopolies in many aspects, are usually formed with a more or less broad regional and temporary influence, although they are always subject to the emergence of new forms of production and competition on a global scale that they cannot permanently prevent.

It is possible to have a theory of the international division of labour and to combine three articulated interpretations that work well within their respective dimensions. First, the theory of the original accumulation of capital, which gives rise to the formation of centres, semi-peripheries, and peripheries, as suggested by David Harvey⁸⁴. Second, the theory of absolute advantages for international trade, which explains the competitive rise of those economic agents that have better relative production and productivity costs, as pointed out by Anwar Shaikh⁸⁵. Third, the idea of empowered labour, which considers that capitalists located in activities with higher levels of productivity are in a better position to appropriate the value created by their workers, value that is greater because the productive

⁸⁴ Harvey 2003.

⁸⁵ Shaikh 2022.

resources they pool are superior on a global scale, as Mandel⁸⁶ and Astarita⁸⁷ argue.

In summary there are several dimensions that are influenced by the course of social and class conflict in each historical process: (1) a process of accumulation by dispossession, according to Harvey,⁸⁸ which leads to an international division of labour of an unequal character, and a value chain dominated by the capital of the great powers protected by their empires; (2) a competitive dynamic, based on the logic of absolute advantages for international trade, according to Shaikh⁸⁹, whose inertia accentuates the real divergence between economies.⁹⁰

The acceptance of the theory of absolute advantage is compatible with acknowledging that an economy's position in the international division of labour can change. This can occur through a shift in endogenous development policies, for example, by leveraging existing advantages. It can also happen through a policy of relative detachment from the influence of hegemonic powers and a subsequent reconnection and reconstruction within new supranational spheres not subordinate to the central powers of the

⁸⁶ Mandel 1999, p. 351.

⁸⁷ Astarita 2015.

⁸⁸ Harvey 2003

⁸⁹ Shaikh 2022, p. 728.

⁹⁰ Montibeler 2009.

global economy. In other words, through policies that counteract the inertial tendencies of international competition.

What we understand is that if there are transfers of value in this way, they take place within competition between capitals, and not so much between countries and even less so within the working class as Astarita (2009) seems to read Mandel's interpretation. Capital, whether domestic or foreign, exploits labour in every market. Then, in global competition driven by unequal exchange, capital from core countries appropriates the surplus generated in peripheral economies.

If the course of a long wave is determined by the evolution of the rate of profit, the question arises as to the incidence of disparate levels of development or of different proportions between the different market spheres: transnational, national or local. The course of accumulation is not synchronous, nor does it follow the same rhythms in all economic regions. In practice, there is a multiplicity of rates of profitability which, while following similar trends, move at different rhythms. Moreover, the rate of profit is not the same for transnational capital as for local capital, for capital from the centre or the periphery or the semi-periphery, for large companies or for small ones. It should be noted that the trend towards equalisation of profit rates implies a regulatory trend over the horizon.

In any case, despite the fact that the analysis of long waves has usually been limited by statistical availability to the Northern powers, Michael Roberts has recently made progress in estimating a 'world rate of profit' by compiling 'a weighted measure of the rate of profit' for the top seven capitalist economies (G7) and also the so-called BRIC economies (Brazil, India, Russia and China).⁹¹ The trends he points to indicate a tendency towards stagnation.

World Market Hegemony is in Dispute

An important question is whether China, with its own endogenous development policies, has created its own long wave for the region and its zone of influence. China has undergone profound changes in recent decades. Large Asian markets, the high rate of exploitation, its Silk Road trade policy, targeted public investment combined with a domestic market economy, endogenous development, all have brought China closer to global economic hegemony. The strength of its domestic accumulation, the role of its industry, its very large labour force, its role as a global creditor, its access to raw materials and the way it is inserted into the global supply chain explain China's

⁹¹ Roberts 2017, 2016, and 2020.

differentiated path. It can be seen as a distinct long wave that, without breaking global patterns, at least follows its own growth rhythm. The new framework of the period, as Claudio Katz⁹² states, is that 'China is rising, the old Triad is losing its pace, and yet global accumulation is weakening'.

We cannot claim that China by itself, even considering adding many other countries that have transitioned to capitalism in one form or another, has caused the eruption of a new long wave. However, the Chinese accumulation regime has allowed the country to aspire to global superpower status. This may be a necessary precondition for a new period of prosperity. But it is not enough, given that China is bound by the burdens of its interdependence with global capitalism⁹³ and has its own contradictions. This rise to superpower status will also have to overcome the obstacles posed by the world's leading military power, the United States. At the same time, China will also have to combine its rise with the formation of a large workers' movement within the country, the largest in the world, which is demanding greater redistribution and social rights. Or with the real estate crises that are shaking it.

⁹² Katz 2019.

⁹³ Vázquez 2021.

An important series of Asian countries have maintained a strong accumulation dynamic. Their economic emergence seems to open the way for a new central hegemonic power, which is not, however, disconnected from the contradictions of capitalist globalisation. China's future development depends chiefly on the development of imports in the markets of the former Triad, on the debt dependence of the US and on the environmental and energy crises. The Asian economy accounts for no more than 25% of the world market. China, as the world's leading trading power, exported 12.8% of the world's goods in 2018, according to the WTO⁹⁴. China is not yet in a position to fully replace the classic powers nor is capable of pulling the world economy on its own. In short, capitalist development continues but has mutated.

Large regional markets with their own institutions and dynamics are being reorganised. This is the case of the Southeast Asian (ASEAN) and Asia-Pacific economic zone, or the Anglophone trading zone (US, UK, Australia), or the intensification of trade ties between China, Russia and other countries in their orbit. These zones are not disconnected from global capitalism, but they adopt a relatively autonomous dynamic. We may be witnessing a more focused

⁹⁴ Vázquez 2021.

adaptation of free trade in each regional market, combined with a growing protectionism of markets in the centres of development. A policy that does not exclude a return to old forms of lobbying in which the great powers demand more openness and preferential treatment from their satellite countries. While it remains to be seen whether this will happen, such an outcome may be more likely if the breakdown of global value chains, which have become overextended, have different weak links and are vulnerable to disruptive conflicts. This has led to a slowdown in the rise of world trade, at least between 2008 (61% of world GDP, its peak) and 2021 (57%), according to OECD sources.

Percent of World Trade and GDP⁹⁵

⁹⁵ Source: Own elaboration based on OCDE Statistics.

The extractive and industrial phases have been shifting to semi-peripheral or emerging countries, with Western investments directed there. It cannot be ruled out that this development can modify the current long wave pattern.

The overall productive fabric is being restructured, concentrating on industrial design, finance, and final commercial distribution in the central countries, while rationalising costs.

China, together with other emerging economies, is becoming the new industrial and commercial supply superpower. It can generate its own extensive areas of global influence and consolidating a state capitalism scheme that reinforces its competitive, investment, production and labour discipline capacity. It employs authoritarian formulas when necessary.

Changes in the Corporate Power System

In this complex context, capitalism has globalised its mercantile and financial spheres and most importantly⁹⁶ has developed globally interconnected production and supply chains. Large firms produce and compete with other global firms in a much larger, international

⁹⁶ Katz 2018.

market, devouring or subordinating local capital. Their gigantism operates through a form of vertical corporate-networking. Network companies and conglomerates allow the concentration of economic power, dominating economically dependent activities, externalising risks and securing the most profitable and secure core business. However, this does not prevent some of the old oligopolies from facing competition, with large technology companies displacing the old, large companies in the commercial, manufacturing and energy sectors, and possibly soon in the financial sector with online banking and virtual currencies.

It is worth mentioning that Big Tech companies represent the main sector of the S&P 500 index. They are the companies with the highest weight in financial markets, around 28% as of July 2023 according to Bloomberg data.⁹⁷ They are also the most profitable ones, despite the decline in stock prices in 2022 from which they already recovered in 2023.

With this dizzying change in the structure of corporate power, in which no oligopoly lasts forever, we must highlight the global emergence of a shadow power.⁹⁸ These are the asset management companies, such as BlackRock, Vanguard or State Street, which

⁹⁷ Menton and Popina 2023. Available at: <<https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2023-07-09/history-says-big-tech-s-dominance-over-us-stocks-poses-no-risk#xj4y7vzkg>>.

⁹⁸ Louçã 2019, p.110.

have penetrated almost all sectors, have decision power over them and obtain profits from them, with a power comparable to that of the largest states. Similarly we have private equity firms such as KKR, Blackstone, Carlyle and Apollo. Undoubtedly capitalism as a socio-historical formation can preserve class power structures over time, although its structures of appropriation, monopoly and exploitation are bound to change constantly.

State Neoliberalism and Financialisation Policies

The downward trend in the rate of profit caused by the crisis of the 1970s was interrupted by socio-political factors. Firstly, by the political and organisational defeat of the workers' movement. Secondly, by the adoption of neo-liberal economic policies by the ruling classes. During this recent period, the old triad of the USA, Europe and Japan applied policies of state neoliberalism. This means a financialised neoliberalism with strong state intervention in favour of capital, which has caused a change of pattern since the 1990s. While the precise dates vary depending on the country, these older policies ran their course in 2008. From 2008 until 2022 an ultra-expansionary monetary policy was introduced to bail out capital, help buy up its corporate debt, privilege its financing, deregulate the credit system and bring

down financial costs. At the same time, regressive taxation was applied, taxing capital, savings and wealth relatively less than consumption and labour. The combination of these policies allowed private debt to be converted and socialised into public debt.

The objective of these policies was to restore the rate of profit. However, its concrete implementation took on a pragmatic character that did not coincide with the theoretical models of the neo-classical school. Actually-existing Neoliberalism has relied heavily on the intervention of the state, albeit in new ways.⁹⁹

If policymakers had followed the advice of orthodox economists, this would have implied: (1) the downward adjustment of wages; (2) privatisation of public services; (3) a restrictive monetary policy; (4) a withdrawal of the state to allow more private initiative without public support.

The first of these points has clearly taken place. As for the second, hybrid formulas of marketisation have been developed which have not rejected public money. This is the case of public-private partnerships and the outsourcing of public services through sub-contracting and concessions. The third has been replaced by loose monetary policy, lax banking regulation and the promotion of massive

⁹⁹ Albarracín, 2021.

securitisation of assets for commercialisation and credit easing. It started in the 1990s and deepened in the Twenty-first century. At least until 2022, when a restrictive monetary policy returned, although the new framework imposed by Trump's second term seems to be returning to expansionary monetary policies.

Finally on the fourth point, the state has intervened more actively, but it has done so to subsidise and bail out private companies, reducing their taxes and partly abandoning welfare policies and the public supply of goods. In other words, the period has been characterised by the predominance of state neoliberalism. A model that does not fit the neoclassical academic doctrine.

All these policies activated countertrends, reinvigorated the economy and postponed recessions, but not without accumulating new contradictions, especially since 2008. With these measures, the rate of exploitation started to grow from the 1980s. Real hourly wages have fallen behind hourly labour productivity since then. Productivity has tended to stagnate, except for one decade (1995–2004) where it was helped by improvements in the field of microelectronics. The lag of real wages behind productivity had recessionary consequences by dampening purchasing power. However, this was compensated by falling interest rates. The gradual but large decline in interest rates from the 1990s onwards made it easier and cheaper to finance

investment and consumption, which increasingly operated on credit. In sum, the effective corporate profit rate rose back to near post-war levels at the beginning of the new millennium. Gross operating profitability increased as labour costs moderated and financial costs became sustainable due to very low interest rates.

This concept of financialisation is also controversial. Some authors give it more importance¹⁰⁰ and others less. The latter place it within the dynamic of capital, not above it.¹⁰¹ Financialisation is making inroads by introducing new mechanisms for capturing the surplus both for the rentier and industrial sectors of capital. There are different kinds of instruments that perform this function: the securitisation of assets, derivatives, shares, participating loans, public debt, obtaining income from real estate and so forth. However, as Katz and Astarita warn, they do not replace the accumulation process but depend and feed from it, they ultimately bring together the interests of industrial and rentier capital.

This dynamic has been exhausted since 2005. The rate of profit began to fall, productivity stagnated and the accumulated costs of financialisation, especially due to high debt accumulation, laid the foundations for the Great Recession of 2008–2013.

¹⁰⁰ Louçã 2019, Chesnais 2019 and Husson 2013.

¹⁰¹ Katz 2018, and Astarita 2009b.

The phenomenon of financial hypertrophy¹⁰² had been foreseen since the late 1990s. Its rise should not lead us to exaggerate the division between rentier and industrial capital. There is no permanent divorce between the rate of profit and accumulation, as economists Dumenil and Levy¹⁰³ claim. It has been a temporary development. The different segments of capital (financial, extractive, logistical, industrial, commercial) are driven by interdependent interests, despite competition. In short, firms compete for the mass of surplus value a posteriori, after it has been extracted from labour, and only afterwards compete for the overall profit. Therefore, the common primary interest of capital is to prioritise the conditions of exploitation and to guarantee the vigour of accumulation.

Public authorities have chosen to confront this crisis with measures that combine wage and labour adjustment, indirect wage cuts, the provision of public services through public-private partnerships – that is, the public financing of private activity – and with formidable quantities of public aid and bailouts. The result has been an unprecedented fiscal crisis and ever-increasing public deficits and state indebtedness. This has been followed by a gigantic operation of converting private debt into public debt, in a new format and with the

¹⁰² See Albarracín 1994.

¹⁰³ Dumenil and Levy 2004.

large-scale socialisation of losses which, with the latest EU measures, has also meant a strong shift of the debt burden to European institutions, and in particular to the European Central Bank.¹⁰⁴

Conclusions

The long-wave concept remains useful. However, for large regional market areas, understood as semi-continental market areas built by characteristic economic and exchange practices and institutions (coinciding with the EU market area in Europe, ASEAN in Asia, USMCA in North America, or with highly relevant economies such as China, India, or the USA...), the wave concept must be delimited and adapted to their own rhythms and asynchronies. This invites us to develop a more coherent model of interpretation based on the articulation of the theory of uneven development and dependency with the theory of long waves.

The pattern and dynamics of waves are continuously being altered because of historical events and processes, and geopolitical

¹⁰⁴ Toussaint et al. 2021 : <https://www.cadtm.org/Why-Euro-zone-countries-debt-to-the-ECB-must-be-cancelled>.

and socio-political changes. The trend towards globalisation moves through a terrain constructed by socio-historical formations that take shape in specific territories and peoples, which give it form, and can temporarily reverse, or break free from pre-established patterns, if there are processes of rupture with the logic of capital.

Is it inevitable, as Sweezy and Baran¹⁰⁵ or, for other reasons, Michael Roberts,¹⁰⁶ that capitalism has entered a stagnationist dynamic that is the result of its internal mechanisms? We cannot generalise and nothing is set in stone. The internal tendencies of capital are not the only thing involved in history, nor are they the same in all parts of the world. On the contrary, the course of struggles, events, victories and defeats, and changes in structures give rise to new phases and waves. For the time being, whether these developments surprise us or we set them in motion through political action, the ecological limits of the planet, the accumulation of debt and the intensification of trade and inter-imperialist wars – of which the war in Ukraine or the colonialist genocide in Palestine are the latest examples – hinder any prosperity. However, we cannot say the same for China or India, which are growing stronger in relation to the countries of the global South, a South which is not stagnating.

¹⁰⁵ Sweezy and Baran 1968.

¹⁰⁶ Robert 2016.

Ultimately, it is up to each era to carry out a concrete analysis of the specific situation, bearing in mind that we are also protagonists, whether by action or omission.

From another point of view, it seems increasingly timely to ask whether the term neoliberalism has become meaningless. Repeatedly, facts force us to add qualifying labels to it. Authoritarian neoliberalism, state neoliberalism, pragmatic neoliberalism, state-directed capitalism... these are perhaps clues that we need to use other terms to refer to the new period.

From this point of view, the implementation of the so-called neoliberal policy responded to the conditions of the new context, but it was the result of a political conflict. The ruling classes of the time waged a strong political, ideological and material battle against the trade unions, which were reduced to a corporate minority or integrated into the so-called social concertation, where they lost their vocation for universal change. The long battle of the 1970s and 1980s resulted in a major political defeat for the labour movement and the forces of change, which either fragmented or accommodated to social liberalism. But this did not come about without an adaptation of the bourgeoisie's measures, as it had to ration and modulate its adjustment policies, displacing some collectives with policies and partially integrating others, legitimising and directing individualistic

aspirations to form the idealised 'middle class'. However, it did so by creating new problems: mainly permanent job insecurity and the ecological and debt crises. All problems which are increasingly difficult to manage.

In the meantime, the new developments in capitalism need to be properly characterised. State neoliberalism is a type of policy that brings together ordoliberal features with certain neo-Keynesian traits favourable to the functioning of large private corporate capital. The state comes into play not as a neutral actor but by playing a leading role in supporting corporate capital, using public funds either to create artificial markets through public procurement or by providing financial aid or subsidies to cover the solvency problems of many companies. The market, in short, requires a lot of (bourgeois) state intervention to function properly.

Mandel's model built a fertile base that offers an analytical architecture that continues to make sense, which requires constant updating in order to understand the structure of the historical moment. On the basis of the above, and of new contributions seen in this article, we can point to certain perspectives: The sum of contradictions and the inability to overcome the crisis of overproduction, together with the socio-ecological limits, augur a long crisis oscillating between weak recovery, stagnation, and depression.

First, the pandemic crisis, then the war, but especially the climate and energy crises will accentuate the objective problems for accumulation. These are the result of the degradation of various environmental dimensions, in addition to the difficulties inherent to capitalist logic.

Finally, if this systemic crisis is not confronted by an organised ecosocialist and feminist alternative, the state neoliberalism applied until now could give way to an authoritarian and disciplinary neoliberalism. The alternative that we continue to imagine and build is a patient, conscious and organised struggle to build an ecosocialist, free, egalitarian and emancipated society.

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